

Research Article

In-Vitro Comparative Evaluation of Anti-Inflammatory Activity of *Tinospora cordifolia* and *Ocimum sanctum*

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ABSTRACT

The emergence of multidrug-resistant pathogens has increased the need for safer and effective alternatives to conventional anti-inflammatory drugs. Medicinal plants rich in phytochemicals offer promising therapeutic potential. The present study evaluates the in-vitro anti-inflammatory activity of aqueous extracts of *Tinospora cordifolia* (Guduchi) and *Ocimum sanctum* (Tulsi) using the protein denaturation method. Both plants have been traditionally used in Ayurveda for managing inflammation, fever, and various chronic disorders. The results showed significant inhibition of protein denaturation by the extracts, with maximum inhibition observed at higher concentrations. The combination of *T. cordifolia* and *O. sanctum* demonstrated greater activity (45.87% inhibition at 200 µg/ml) compared to individual extracts. These findings indicate that the synergistic use of these plant extracts could serve as a cost-effective and natural alternative for the management of inflammatory conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Inflammation is a complex biological response of tissues to harmful stimuli such as pathogens, injury, or chemical irritants. While essential for host defense, prolonged or uncontrolled inflammation contributes to chronic diseases including arthritis, diabetes, cardiovascular disorders, and cancer [1].

The rising incidence of drug-resistant pathogens and side effects of synthetic anti-inflammatory drugs highlight the urgent need for novel, safer alternatives [2,3]. Medicinal plants, long used in Ayurveda and other traditional systems, provide an effective reservoir of bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, and phenolics with proven anti-inflammatory properties [4,5].

Tinospora cordifolia (Guduchi) and *Ocimum sanctum* (Tulsi) are well-documented medicinal

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plants in Ayurveda. *T. cordifolia* is known for its immunomodulatory, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities, while *O. sanctum* is revered as an adaptogen with antimicrobial, anti-stress, and anti-inflammatory effects. This study investigates the comparative in-vitro anti-inflammatory potential of their aqueous extracts.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

Aim:

To evaluate and compare the in-vitro anti-inflammatory activity of aqueous extracts of *Tinospora cordifolia* and *Ocimum sanctum*.

Objectives:

1. To prepare aqueous extracts of *T. cordifolia* and *O. sanctum*.
2. To evaluate anti-inflammatory activity by the protein denaturation method.
3. To compare the activity of individual extracts and their combination against the standard drug diclofenac sodium.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and Authentication

Leaves of *Tinospora cordifolia* and *Ocimum sanctum* were procured from local markets in Andhra Pradesh, India, and authenticated by a botanist.

Preparation of Extracts

60 g of powdered leaves of each plant were subjected to aqueous extraction using 500 ml distilled water for 48 hours. Extracts were filtered using Whatman No.1 filter paper, concentrated, and stored in a desiccator for further use.

In-vitro Anti-inflammatory Activity

The activity was assessed using the protein denaturation method [10,11]:

- **Reaction mixture:** 0.2 ml egg albumin + 2.8 ml phosphate buffer saline (pH 6.4) + 2 ml plant extract at varying concentrations.
- **Control:** Distilled water.
- **Incubation:** 37 °C for 15 min, followed by heating at 70 °C for 5 min.
- Absorbance was measured at 660 nm.
- Diclofenac sodium was used as standard.

% Inhibition was calculated as:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{(\text{Acontrol} - \text{Asample}) \times 100}{\text{Acontrol}}$$

Statistical Analysis

All experiments were performed in triplicate (n=3). Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's post-hoc test to compare differences between groups. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of *T. cordifolia* Extract

At 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, inhibition reached $41.35 \pm 1.2\%$, which was statistically lower ($p < 0.05$) than diclofenac ($46.3 \pm 0.9\%$).

Effect of *O. sanctum* Extract

At 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, inhibition was $44.43 \pm 1.0\%$, showing no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) compared with diclofenac ($46.3 \pm 0.9\%$).

Effect of Combination

The combined extracts exhibited maximum inhibition of $45.87 \pm 0.8\%$ at 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The effect

was statistically higher than *T. cordifolia* alone ($p < 0.05$), but comparable with *O. sanctum* and diclofenac ($p > 0.05$).

These findings suggest a synergistic effect when both plant extracts are combined. Protein denaturation is a well-established mechanism in inflammation and autoimmune disorders [10,11]. The ability of extracts to inhibit denaturation highlights their anti-inflammatory efficacy. The results are consistent with previously reported pharmacological activities of *T. cordifolia* and *O. sanctum*[6–9].

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrates that aqueous extracts of *Tinospora cordifolia* and *Ocimum sanctum* exhibit significant in-vitro anti-inflammatory activity. The combination of both extracts showed greater inhibition than individual extracts, indicating synergistic potential. Statistical analysis confirmed that the activity of the combination was significantly higher than *T. cordifolia* alone and comparable to diclofenac sodium. These results support the traditional use of these plants and suggest their application in developing safe, effective, and affordable herbal formulations for managing inflammation.

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